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Data Review

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Abstract

The Business Environment and Enterprise Performance Survey (BEEPS) is a firm-level survey conducted by the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development and the World Bank Group to assess (perceived) business conditions in transition economies. Covering multiple waves from 1999 to 2020, it includes a wide range of post-Soviet and Eastern European countries (with the exception of Turkmenistan), although regional coverage varies across rounds. The survey uses stratified random sampling of formally registered firms and is based on interviews with firm owners / managers. It collects data on firm characteristics, their access to finance, taxation, perceptions of corruption levels, and other aspects of the business environment in a particular country. Access to the data is currently being updated, while data documentation can already be studied.

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Review of the Business Environment and Enterprise Performance Survey by Stas Gorelik

The Business Environment and Enterprise Performance Survey (BEEPS) is a firm-level survey conducted jointly by the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) and the World Bank Group. Five main rounds of BEEPS have been conducted so far: 1999–2000, 2002, 2005, 2008–2009, and 2012–2016. A subsequent round, covering 2018–2020, was implemented jointly by the EBRD, the European Investment Bank, and the World Bank Group. Across these rounds, the project expanded both its geographical and substantive coverage. At the same time, key questions were retained, allowing for broad longitudinal comparisons.

For scholars of the post-Soviet region and the Baltic states, the project's extensive geographical coverage is particularly useful, although it is not identical across waves. The first round (1999–2000) included Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Estonia, Georgia, Kazakhstan, the Kyrgyz Republic, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Russia, Ukraine, and Uzbekistan. Tajikistan was added in 2002. Turkmenistan is absent from all waves, which is not surprising given the country's closed and repressive political regime. Moreover, during the fifth round (2012–2016), fieldwork in Russia covered more than 30 regions (with over 4,000 enterprises surveyed), enabling subnational analysis of the business environment within Russia (albeit now somewhat dated).

In terms of sampling, the project relies on stratified random sampling of formally registered firms, based on business registers or statistical lists. Fieldwork—face-to-face interviews with firm owners and senior managers—has been carried out by local survey organizations; Within each country, firms are stratified by sector, size, and location to ensure adequate representation across different segments. In most cases, the target population includes private, formally registered firms with at least five employees. In addition, some firms surveyed in earlier waves were re-interviewed in later rounds, allowing for the construction of limited panel datasets.

The questionnaires cover several aspects of firm operations. Core modules include firm characteristics, workforce composition, and access to finance. They also address taxation, licensing, corruption, and other informal practices. Moreover, later rounds introduced modules on innovation and practices related to the development of a green economy.

Several limitations of the data are worth noting. First, although the survey retains a number of consistent questions across waves, parts of the questionnaire and methodology have changed over time. This is particularly the case for the 2008–2009 wave, when the survey instrument was harmonized with the World Bank Enterprise Surveys.

Second, as noted above, the project covers only formally registered firms above a certain size threshold, excluding smaller firms and those operating in the informal sector, which may be especially important in transitional economies. Third, because the data are based on interviews with firm representatives, responses may reflect subjective perceptions and biases rather than actual institutional conditions. Respondents may also provide socially desirable answers or avoid discussing sensitive practices, such as bribery or other forms of informal interaction with government officials.

Access to the data is currently in a transitional stage. The EBRD's website provides questionnaires, sampling documentation, and methodological materials. However, it also indicates that firm-level data will be made available for download once released (Stata, Excel, and CSV formats).